

GLUCOSE CONTROL IN ARTIFICIAL PANCREAS SCHEME WITH PID AND PSO-OPTIMIZED PID CONTROLLERS

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Introduction

Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM) patients are using artificial pancreas (AP) implementations [1], which aim to replace or support pancreatic functionality by regulating insulin production. A significant amount of research has been conducted to explore glucose control options for commercial applications employing PID-based control formulations [1] to optimize glucose production, particularly to insulin dosing calculation. This work presents an AP scheme using a continuous PID controller, which is shown to outperform rival particle swarm optimization (PSO) [2]-tuned PID control schemes in a case study also incorporating exogenous glucose disturbance.

Materials & Methods

Simulation has been performed in MATLAB/Simulink environment and includes the following parts:

I) Mathematical model for human body: T1DM patient is modeled by Bergmans' Minimal Model [1]

II) Continuous glucose monitoring sampled every 1 min outputting a running mean of 5 samples.

III) Insulin pump algorithm:

$$u(t) = Basal + \frac{G(t) - G_{target}(t)}{ISF} \quad (1.1)$$

where $\frac{G(t) - G_{target}(t)}{ISF}$ is bounded between 0 and $Bolus_{max}$.

IV) Continuous Parallel PID controller is described by:

$$PID = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(t) + K_D \frac{de(t)}{dt} \quad (1.2)$$

V) PSO framework (ITAE and MAPE obj. functions):

$$v_i(t+1) = wv_i(t)c_1r_1(p_{best,i} - x_i(t)) + \dots c_2r_2(g_{best} - x_i(t)) \quad (1.3)$$

$$y_i(t+1) = \begin{cases} y_i(t), & \text{if } f(x_i(t+1)) \geq f(y_i(t)) \\ x_i(t+1), & \text{if } f(x_i(t+1)) < f(y_i(t)) \end{cases} \quad (1.4)$$

$$\hat{y}_i(t+1) = \arg \min_{y_i} f(y_i(t+1)) \quad (1.5)$$

$$x_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + v_i(t+1) \quad (1.6)$$

Table 1: Simulation Metrics

Obj.Function (f)	PSO-PID MAPE	PSO-PID ITAE	Proposed PID -
T_0 to T_{dist}			
Steady-state error	3.030	3.033	2.071
MSE	11.970	11.981	8.180
MAPE	5.311	5.313	4.155
MACA	0.829	0.828	0.876
MAPA	17.497	17.495	18.313
T_{dist+1} to T_{end}			
Steady-state error	0.474	0.476	0.429
MSE	4.063	4.069	1.116
MAPE	5.563	5.569	4.601
MACA	1.379	1.379	1.559
MAPA	24.643	24.643	26.418

Figure 1: Full AP closed loop simulation results

Metrics Used

Controllers' performance was evaluated using MSE, which quantifies the mean squared deviation from the setpoint, MAPE, which represents the mean absolute percentage error, and steady-state error (SSE), which corresponds to the error in the last sample for each of the two predefined time periods T_0 - T_{dist} and T_{dist+1} - T_{end} . MACA measures mean absolute controller actions to determine more conservative or aggressive behavior, while MAPA quantifies pump actions.

Experimental Results

The case study models a T1DM patient consuming a 50g-carbohydrate rich meal at $T_{dist}=700$ min. Results of the simulation (Table 1 and Figure 1) show that the proposed control scheme leverages the controller's dynamics to a greater extent by performing more aggressive control actions (higher MACA) compared to the other controllers. It also utilizes the pump more efficiently, reflected in higher MAPA. Consequently, the proposed scheme operates more efficiently, achieving better performance in steady-state error, MSE and MAPE. This improvement comes at the cost of a trivial increase in overshoot. Future work will evaluate the results across a wider range of virtual patient scenarios and will also focus on more advanced control techniques, such as Model Predictive Control (MPC) schemes.

References

- [1] S. Echajei, *et al.* (2025) Implementation of PID control strategies on Bergman model representing Type 1 Diabetes-T1D, *Commun. Math. Biol. Neurosci.*, **2025**:1.
- [2] A. Kapnopoulos and A. Alexandridis (2022) A cooperative particle swarm optimization approach for tuning an MPC-based quadrotor trajectory tracking scheme, *Aerospace Science and Technology* **127**:107725.

Keywords: Artificial pancreas, T1DM, PSO, PID control